

THE IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION SECURITY IN THE DOMESTIC PUBLIC POLICY OF AMIR TEMUR

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Annotation. In this article envisaged the information security of internal and external policy in Amir Temur's state. There has talved about tne functions and responsibilities of agents in the spheres such as ensuring the peace and security, tne diplomatic relations and well-reighbourhood polic with other countries of Temur's Empire.

Key words. Amir Temur, external policy, internal policy, diplomatic relation, information security, friendly attitude, ambassador, agents, news, fib news.

In gaining a great life experience, in managing the state with justice, in securing simultaneously peace and security throughout the whole empire, finally, in restoring and strengthening economic relations through the Great Silk Road with the countries of East and West, in establishing strongly the diplomatic relations Amir Temur's extremely deep and comprehensive knowledge, ability to think broadly and deeply, his strong logic played a great role.

In insuring the security of Amir Temur's state his internal and external policy played a very big role. The diplomatic relations of Sahibqiron's empire established with other countries, mutually good neighborly relation in the sphere of commerce played an extremely important role in providing the state security.

Since ancient times our ancestors have adhered to laws and rules of international diplomatic relations and developed this area. Since ancient times our hospitable people have striven to respect other peoples, to establish friendly relations with them. In the diplomacy of Amir Temur, there had always been priority ideas to keep peace, mutual respect, pardoning the rivals and creating good opportunities for them, valuing envoys under any difficult circumstances, observing strictly the diplomatic rules, inviability of man's life and humanism.

As stated by our President Sh. Mirziyoyev: "if we take as an example our grand-grandfather Amir Temur and the Temurids' empire, during the years of ruling by this generation we would witness how great had been the diplomatic relations in our ancient land. At the same time, on the pages of history there are preserved names of such envoys

as Muhammad Keshi from Shahrizabz, as well as Mavlono Hofiz, Ghiyosiddin Naqqosh, Abdurazzoq Samarqandiy who represented Amir Temur and the Temurids' empire in the countries of Europe and Asia" [1].

This is vividly proved by the fact that our grand-grandfather Sahibqiron had established diplomatic relations and exchange of messages with the rulers of many states, such as France, England, Spain, Byzantine, Egypt, China, India and with the empire of Osmania It is well known from history that tens of envoys visited Amir Temur's palace from different countries of the world. The sources of the years between 1389 and 1398 mentioned that on behalf of Amir Temur the envoys had visited China nine times.

For sure, in conducting foreign policy with other countries on the basis of equal rights and in developing diplomatic relations the role of state's envoy is extremely great. It was always required that an envoy had to know his rights and obligations completely well and had to fulfil hi functions and tasks with all his heart and might. Regarding this: "while speaking about the duty and tasks of an envoy before his people and Motherland, about his professional skill, spiritual world, there arises a question: first of all, what features and characters must an Uzbek diplomat, ambassador of today possess? It is clearly seen that the word "ambassador" denotes a representative of his country, people, who connects peoples and countries with each other" [2].

The diplomacy of Sahibqiron Amir Temur has developed in harmony with the world community and reflected in itself fully the features of those times. It is necessary to state separately that at those times Central Asia had become the center of the world diplomacy" [3].

At those times among the rulers of Europe, Castilian and Leon's King Don Enrich III had treated Asia with a special interest. In 1402 as he sent his envoys to the small Asia, he ordered the envoys "to collect information about the traditions, customs, conduct, morals, religions, faith, power and goals to benefit him" [4].

While speaking about the diplomacy of Amir Temur, it is necessary to emphasize the memories of Ruy Gonzalez de Clavijo. Clavijo was Spain's envoy sent to the palace of Amir Temur by Castilian and Leon's King Don Enrich III. He had lived in the palace between the years 1403-1406 and had written in his memory diary what he had seen in Temur's empire. During the period when the emperor of Constantinople had left for Europe to ask assistance, that is, in the summer of 1402 Amir Temur sent the priest Francie with a diplomatic letter of credentials to the deputy of the Emperor. At the same time, in the letter kept in the archive of Venus Amir Temur had written that Sahibqiron received the priest Francie, he had liked the monarch, that he had requested

twenty military ships from the emperor of Trapeze for mutual union, as well as he made it known that had sent envoys to Baized in the accompaniment of priest Francie [5].

At that time independent Tarabzun situated on the Southern - Eastern shores of the Black sea used to be an important port of Greek Christian Kingdom, and served as a big mediator on the trade road between South and West where the merchants of Genuya had an upper hand. The fact that this kingdom expressed its subordination to Amir Temur confirms how influential the diplomatic relations of Sahibqiron were at that time.

Thus, if in the foreign policy of the state the more important was the role of envoys, in defining problems among people the more careful was the work of so called arzbegi, an internal informant. The arzbegi had to inform Amir Temur about the internal policy, that is, about the conditions of soldiers, community people as well as received applicants of complaints, what important works had been fulfilled, and what deeds had to be performed.

As Amir Temur wrote in his "Institutes", "I ordained that on every frontier, and in every country, and in every city, and in every camp a writer of intelligence should be established; and that each should write to the imperial presence, with truth and perspicuity, full accounts of the conduct and the behavior of the governors, and of the officers; and of the soldiers, and of the subjects; and of the state of my own armies, and of those of foreign powers; and of the bringing in, and the carrying out of all merchandize and commodities; and of the entrance, and the departure of all strangers, and of all Caravans of every country; and of the transactions of the neighboring kingdoms and princes, and of their conduct and behavior; and also of the learned and skillful men of distant countries, who might turn their faces towards my dominions:

And that if the writer of the intelligence was guilty of falsehood, and wrote not the true state of the facts, his fingers should be cut off: and that if he suppressed the laudable actions of the soldier, or wrote an unjust account thereof, he should be deprived of his right hand: and that if he wrote a false account from enmity and from malice, he should be put to death. And I commanded that these accounts should be transmitted unto me day by day, and week by week, and month by month" [6].

And I ordained, that a thousand swift camel-men and a thousand horse-men, and a thousand expeditious footmen should be selected; and that they should inform themselves of the occurrences of the countries, and of the frontiers; and of the intentions and the designs of the neighboring princes; and that they should return unto the presence, and give me information thereof, that I might provide the remedy before the

evil arrived” [7]. It would not be mistake if we say that by this Amir Temur stated several centuries ago that the informant should write only the truth in describing the event and delivering to somebody, that the false and slander would cause the violation of human rights. Naturally, we can say today that all these principles have found their reflection in our legislation.

About it Husayin Voiz Koshifi wrote in his work “Akhloqi Muhsini” (“Conduct of Muhsini”): “For Padishahs the center of empire, that is, a castle is like a courtyard for an ordinary man, the city and deserts are under his protection, there living any poor or needed has a neighboring right, the Padishah should be and must be aware of their state” [8].

As Amir Temur wrote in his “Institutes”, I sent a letter to my friends in the service of Amir Husayin and asked them to warn me of his deceits. Once one of my friends Sher Bahrom warned me of Amir Husayin’s evil intention. Amir Husayin noticed it and had Sher Bahrom murdered, and launched a fight against me with a thousand horse-men.

Amir Temur was well aware that in insuring the security and stability a great role was given to rulers’ alertness, watchfulness and entrepreneurship, in case he is weak, simple and had trust in everything, the insecurity inside the country might cause instability in the state itself. Besides, he considered that breaking laws, not adhering to them would finally cause injustice and instability in the country.

Sh. Uljayeva states that “If we think of the international situation, it should be emphasized separately that Amir Temur’s period was the period of violations, informational struggle. It was required that in order to keep security and stability of his country one should watch political events going on in the neighboring states with alertness” [9].

It was a must that in applying just punishments to crimes the informants had to send notes from the most remote lands of the empire. If an informant hides the service of a soldier or an official or deceits about him or wrote false information, as soon as his deed was proved, his hands were cut off. If he did not write the events intentionally, his fingers were cut off. If the informant wrote false information with slander or with evil intention, he was murdered. The information was delivered to Amir Temur day by day, week by week, month by month. (“Sultans should and must have officials of state bodies and applauders, other civil servants and keens (regions and people, Padishah’s relatives and children – M.A.). Because if one of the Padishahs possessed some of the land property, if all wills of people belong to him, he must be aware of the general and each situation of his country in accordance with laws and alertness, must take care if

his people, ministers and those under his rule, he must also know big or small officials of his country. The informants should deliver information regularly and keep him informed of the situation, if the situation of regions and peoples, surrounding lands and places were hidden from the Padishah, it would cause a very big damage to the country” [10].

Amir Temur understood well that it was more important to prevent the danger than to fight against it, that’s why he considered that the events happening in neighboring states are indivisible with the security of his own state. In order to be aware of the situation in other countries he had sent his spies to these countries under the mask of sheikhs of these lands, merchants, beggars and other masks, consequently he determined his foreign policy in consistent with situation. The information facts received from tourists, merchants, sorceries were considered in the closed door meetings and the threat to endanger the indivisibility of the country was prevented in time [11].

If to sum up, some of the guests who arrived from abroad under the masks of merchants, sheikhs and other names used to visit us with other intentions. Accordingly, Movarounnahr the informants were sent o other states and they used to inform about the evets happening in strange countries. Amir Temur appointed a thousand swift camel-men and a thousand horse-men, and a thousand expeditious footmen as responsible informants on roads and robots to find out the intentions of the people coming abroad. These events served as the guarantee of regional peace during the Temurids’ period.

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